

THE INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *Modernization of education system in our country is closely linked with the implementation of innovative technologies into the process of teaching and modernizing the content and methods of education. Modern society needs well educated and qualified specialists who are able to creative thinking and feeling responsibility in solving difficult problems.*

Key words: *personal potential, teaching process, personality, ability, interests, the organization of the teaching process*

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Annotatsiya: *Mamlakatimizda ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiya qilish o'qitish jarayoniga innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish, ta'lim mazmuni va usullarini modernizatsiya qilish bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Zamonaviy jamiyat ijodiy fikrlashga qodir, murakkab muammolarni hal qilishda mas'uliyatni his qila oladigan bilimli va malakali mutaxassislarga muhtoj.*

Kalit so'zlar: *shaxsiy salohiyat, o'qitish jarayoni, shaxs, qobiliyat, qiziqish, o'qitish jarayonini tashkil etish*

Аннотация: *Модернизация образования в нашей стране тесно связана с внедрением в учебный процесс инновационных технологий, модернизацией содержания и методов обучения. Общество способно к творческому мышлению, нуждается в*

образованной и квалифицированной помощи для развития ответственности в решении современных задач.

***Ключевые слова:** личностный потенциал, учебный процесс, личность, способности, интересы, организация учебного процесса.*

The main attention here is focused on the personal interests of the pupils and their personal potential. And this demands different approach to the learners of a foreign language taking into consideration their personality, ability, interests. That is why the main problem for the teacher is to choose the correct methods and aids of teaching which are very effective in getting the aim of teaching. In the late years the new informational technologies are being widely used in the teaching process at schools too. It is not only the use of new technical aids but also the use of new forms, methods of teaching and the new approach in the organization of the teaching process.

Teaching young learners

Early teaching English today appears as an innovative process that pedagogy is understood as a managed process of creation, perception, assessment, development and use of pedagogical innovations. The younger school age is characterized by globally operating game motivation at children, and on condition of the correct organization of educational process and the accounting of this factor development of a foreign language by the child will be rather effective.

By the new economic and socio-political conditions of English proficiency is one of the necessary conditions for a genuine nation's competitiveness. English, taking a priority position among other foreign languages, becoming a mandatory component of teaching not only in high schools, secondary, high school, but in elementary school.

In Uzbekistan, the English language is supposed to learn from the 1-st grade, which is a sign of the objectively existing social interest in his studies and confirms the importance of this subject for the implementation of long-term objectives and personal development of the state.

Nowadays the problem of early teaching consists in need to improve and perfect the teaching organization not to miss and take advantage of the sensitive period of assimilation of a foreign language. Proper use of the sensitive features of this age contributes to a language base, interest in the English language, and through him to the people, culture and country of the target language as a whole. This affects the development of the child, his cognitive, thinking, communication skills, broaden their horizons.

Starting to learn English, the child has difficulty not in the mastery of them and in the sociopsychological relationship with a teacher or peers. He still lacks communication skills. The aims of the adult – to develop them, to create such conditions that the child wanted to communicate. On this account there is no single opinion. Some educators practitioners believe that «The best — talk to the child in a foreign language from the date of his birth. It develops hearing, gives an idea of the sound diversity of the world» [1].

What is early age?

L.S. Vygotsky, S.I. Rubinstein, and foreign psychology B. Whyte, J. Bruner, V. Penfield, R. Roberts, Eliot, told that the child masters a foreign language easier than the adult. Duration sensitive period is characterized differently by different authors: Penfield and Roberts define it with 4 to 8 years, Eliot — from 5 to 7 years.

The four-year primary education is seen as the first stage of a new 12-year school, before which setting the aim, to achieve global trends of education development. At the primary level the personality of the young schoolboy, to identify and develop his abilities, forming skills and desire to learn, mastering the elements of the culture of speech and behavior. The fact that a 12-year school to learn a foreign language is offered with 1-st grade is a recognition of the objectively existing social interest in the study of foreign languages and confirms the importance of this subject for the implementation of long-term objectives of personality development. For example, such as the increase in the average level of education, increase the requirements for the general culture, the formation of readiness for international cooperation. Given the results of more than forty years of research in the field of early teaching foreign languages, which were carried out in our country, along with extensive experience in teaching, it can be argued that its advantage is repeatedly proven. Briefly

summarizing the advantages of systematic teaching children a foreign language in primary school age is useful for all children, regardless of starting abilities, because it provides [2]:

- the indisputable positive impact on the mental functions of the child: his memory, attention, thinking, perception, imagination, ;
- make the child an active participant in the educational process;
- provide variety and frequent changes of methods and forms of education;
- promote the interests of children, to develop their desire to learn and thus make a real achievement of academic success;
- stimulating influence on the general speech ability of the child;
- early teaching a foreign language gives great practical effect in terms of improving the quality of owning the first foreign language, provides the basis for continuing his studies at the basic school;
- unique educational and informative value of early foreign language teaching, which manifests itself in an earlier entry of the child to human culture through communication on new language [3].

Ability to competently teach a foreign language communication junior high school pupils who are not yet fully proficient communicative skills in their native language — a task very difficult and responsibly. Interest in the subject at an early age is very closely linked with the sense of psychological comfort, needs and readiness to communicate, which makes the teacher at a lesson. The success of the teaching and attitudes of students to the subject depends on how interesting and emotionally teacher conducts lessons.

The problem of teaching of younger students

The problem of teaching of younger students requires a different methodological approach than teaching elders. The main assistant in this case can be a game [4].

Elkonin believes that the game is social in nature and direct saturation and projected to reflect the adult world. Calling the game «arithmetic of social relations», D.B. Elkonin treats the

game as an activity that occurs at a certain stage, as one of the leading forms of mental functions and ways of knowing the child of the adult

By definition of M.F. Stronin: «Game — this type of activity in terms of situations, aimed at recreating and assimilation of social experience, which develops and improves self-behavior» [5].

Due to gaming methods students can easily overcome the language barrier, feel more relaxed in the classroom passes tension, fear, embarrassment.

Applying the lessons of game technology becomes an active teacher assistant, its main function — the organization and stimulation of the educational process. The pupil becomes the main acting figure.

Skills and knowledge acquired in the course of the game can be used in practice and everyday life for: social adaptation in the process of mutual understanding oral and written communication with native speakers, establishing interpersonal and intercultural contacts within easy access.

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